

Comparison Report of Calibration Factor Measurement of Power Sensor with VNA

EPM 22RPT04 RfMicrowave2

RF Power Sensor Calibration with Vector Network Analyzer

Final report

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1. Introduction

A comparison on RF Power Sensor Calibration with Vector Network Analyser (VNA) was planned among the partners of the EPM (European Partnership on Metrology) 22RPT04 RFMicrowave2 project. This inter-laboratory comparison exercise was part of the project “Development of RF and Microwave Metrology Capability II” (22RPT04 ‘RFMicrowave2’), under Work Package (WP) 1.2. titled “RF power measurement and power sensor calibration (Calibration Factor) using a VNA”.

The comparison was planned for six participants (TÜBİTAK, GUM, TRESICAL, CMI, SIQ, and SPARK) involved in WP 1.2 of “22RPT04 RFMicrowave2” Project. SIQ was withdrawn from the comparison after it had started. The comparison was run according to the prepared protocol [1].

TÜBİTAK UME was acting as the pilot institute. The travelling standards were provided by SPARK. TÜBİTAK UME was responsible to monitoring standard performance before and after the circulation and the evaluation and reporting of the comparison results.

The comparison was performed by measuring two power sensors. First power sensor has N type connector and second power sensor has 3.5 mm connector. First and second power sensors are measured at 50 MHz, 1 GHz, 10 GHz, 15 GHz, 18 GHz frequencies @ 0 dBm power range and measured at 50 MHz, 1 GHz, 10 GHz, 20 GHz, 26.5 GHz frequencies @ 0 dBm power range respectively.

2. Participants of the Comparison

2.1. Participants

List of participating laboratories is given in Table 1.

Table 1. List of participating laboratories

Country	Institute/ Participant	Acronym	Shipping Address	Contact Person
Türkiye	TÜBİTAK Ulusal Metroloji Enstitüsü	TÜBİTAK UME	TÜBİTAK Ulusal Metroloji Enstitüsü TÜBİTAK Gebze Yerleşkesi Barış Mah. Dr. Zeki Acar Cad. No:1 41470 Gebze-Kocaeli, TÜRKİYE	Erkan DANACI erkan.danaci@tubitak.gov.tr
Türkiye	SPARK Kalibrasyon Hizmetleri Anonim Şirketi	SPARK	Spark Ölçüm Teknolojileri A.Ş. M.Kemal Mah.Dumlupınar Bul.No:274 Mahall Ankara B Blok No:104 06510 Çankaya Ankara TÜRKİYE	Samet AKLAR samet_aklar@sparkmeasure.com
Czechia	Cesky Metrologicky Institut	CMI	Cesky Metrologicky Institut Radiova 1136/3 CZ-10200 Praha 10 CZECH REPUBLIC	Jan GRAJCIAR Jan.grajciar@cmi.cz Tel: +420 266 020 174 Fax: +420 266 020 169
Poland	Central Office of Measures	GUM	Główny Urząd Miar Elektoralna 2 00-139 Warszawa POLAND	Łukasz USYDUS lukasz.usydus@gum.gov.pl
Denmark	Trescal A/S	Trescal	Trescal A/S Mads Clausens Vej 12 DK-8600 Silkeborg DENMARK	Torsten LIPPERT torsten.lippert@trescal.com

Slovenia	Slovenski Institut za Kakovost in Meroslovje	SIQ	Slovenski Institut za Kakovost in Meroslovje (SIQ) Mašera-Spasičeva 10 SI-1000 Ljubljana SLOVENIA	Marko BERGINC marko.berginc@siq.si Tel: +386 1 4778 340
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2.2. Pilot Institute

This comparison was piloted by TÜBİTAK UME. The pilot institute is responsible for preparing the comparison protocol, controlling the stability of the travelling standard, analyzing the results, and preparing the comparison report.

3. Organisation of the Comparison

3.1. The time schedule

The time schedule for the comparison is given in Table 2. The circulation of travelling standard was organized so that to monitor the performance of the travelling standard. Each laboratory had 2 weeks to carry out the measurements and 2 weeks for transportation.

Table 2. Circulation Time Schedule

Acronym of Institute	Country	Starting Date	Time for measurement and transportation
TÜBİTAK UME	Türkiye	15 August 2025	2 weeks
SPARK	Türkiye	15 September 2025	2 weeks
CMI	Czechia	05 November 2025	2 weeks
GUM	Poland	19 November 2025	2 weeks
Trescal	Denmark	03 December 2025	2 weeks

3.2. Unexpected events

No damage was reported to the travelling standards during the comparison.

4. Travelling Standard

The travelling standards, Agilent N8481A (first) Power Sensor and Keysight U2063XA (second) Power Sensor have identifications in Figure 1.

Agilent N8481A (first) power sensor, henceforth denoted by the N type standard, has N Type male connector. This power sensor can be used with the N1913A or N1914A power meter. Power sensor has been specified between -35 dBm and +20 dBm power range. Within the comparison, only 0 dBm power was measured.

Keysight U2063XA (second) power sensor, henceforth denoted by the 3.5 mm standard, has a 3.5 mm male connector and a USB connection for an external PC, this power sensor can be used with N1913A or N1914A power meter or standalone. The power sensor has been specified for a power range of -70 dBm to +26 dBm. Within the comparison, only 0 dBm power was measured.

Figure 1. The travelling standards

Quantity in the comparison is Calibration Factor (CF), which is defined by;

$$CF = \frac{P_{DC}}{P_{IN}}$$

with;

P_{DC} – the DC power measured by the power meter,

P_{IN} – the RF power incident in the Power Sensor (travelling standard) at the measurement frequency.

Participants submitted measurement results for the first travelling standard at 5 (five) frequencies (50 MHz, 1 GHz, 10 GHz, 15 GHz, 18 GHz) concerning its calibration factor and reflection coefficient, both with an extended uncertainty (coverage factor $k=2$).

Participants submitted measurement results for the second travelling standard at 5 (five) frequencies (50 MHz, 1 GHz, 10 GHz, 20 GHz, 26.5 GHz) concerning its calibration factor and reflection coefficient, both with an extended uncertainty (coverage factor $k=2$).

The travelling standards supplied by SPARK. These standards were chosen for their common usage, frequency and power range. The general specifications of the travelling standards are given in Table 3.

Table 3. The general specifications of travelling standards

Travelling Standard	N8481A	U2063XA
Operating Frequency	10 MHz to 18 GHz	10 MHz to 33 GHz
Maximum Power	100 mW (average)	398 mW (average)
Connector Type	Type N male	3.5 mm male
Maximum SWR	1.14 (30 MHz to 50 MHz) 1.08 (50 MHz to 2 GHz) 1.16 (2 GHz to 12.4 GHz) 1.23 (12.4 GHz to 18 GHz)	1.24 (30 MHz to 50 MHz) 1.24 (50 MHz to 2 GHz) 1.27 (2 GHz to 12.4 GHz) 1.40 (12.4 GHz to 18 GHz)
Dimensions	Height 30 mm Width 38 mm Long 130 mm	Height 36 mm Width 48 mm Long 169 mm
Weight	181 gram	300 gram

5. Measurement Instructions

The measurement instructions, describing the preliminary operations to be performed on the travelling standard, were given in the Technical Protocol. The measurements were performed with a Vector Network Analyser by using VNA Based Power Sensor Calibration (VBPSC) software. The VBPSC software developed by the external project partner METU (Middle East Technical University). This software has capability for CF uncertainty calculations according to Law of Propagation (LoP) and Monte Carlo Simulations (MCS) methods. Measurements were carried out at five different frequencies for the Calibration Factor, in accordance with the Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM).

6. Measurement Quantities and Points

The quantities to be measured and the measurement frequency points are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Measurement quantities & points

Quantity	Measurement Frequencies (GHz) for First Power Sensor	Measurement Frequencies (GHz) for Second Power Sensor
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Calibration Factor	50 MHz	50 MHz
	1 GHz	1 GHz
	10 GHz	10 GHz
	15 GHz	20 GHz
	18 GHz	26.5 GHz

7. Temperature and humidity during the comparison measurements

Laboratory conditions of the comparison participants were given in Table 5.

Table 5. Laboratory conditions of the comparison participants

Acronym of Institute	Country	Temperature °C	Relative Humidity %rh
TÜBİTAK UME	Türkiye	23 ± 1	45 ± 15
SPARK	Türkiye	23 ± 3	40 ± 20
CMI	Czechia	22.3 ± 1	30.1 ± 15
GUM	Poland	22.7 ± 1	43.5 ± 15
Trescal	Denmark	23 ± 1	40 ± 15

8. Measurement Results of Participants

Each participant institute and laboratory used Vector Network Analyser with VBpsc software to measure the Calibration Factor of the travelling standards.

The comparison was performed by measuring two power sensors. The participants' measurement results were given in Appendix 2. Calibration factor values and their LoP uncertainties of the comparison participants are given in Table 6 and Table 7. Calibration factor values and their MCS uncertainties of the comparison participants are given in Table 8 and Table 9. Some of the participant values are absent in Table 6-9 since the participants did not declare their results for this comparison.

The uncertainties of measurement were calculated by VBpsc software according to GUM (Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM), JCGM 100:2008) for the confidence level of 95 %. The participants' uncertainties were also given in Appendix 2 [2].

Table 6. Calibration Factors and their LoP uncertainties of the comparison participants for N Type Standard power sensor

Labs	TÜBİTAK UME		SPARK		CMI		GUM		Trescal		Reference Value	
	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	y	$u(y)$ (k=1)
50 MHz			0.9982	0.0027	0.9980	0.0060	0.9994	0.0054	0.9970	0.0090	0.9983	0.0044
1 GHz	0.9932	0.0059	0.9925	0.0053	0.9920	0.0080	0.9924	0.0054	0.9930	0.0090	0.9926	0.0056
10 GHz	0.966	0.012	0.9685	0.0068	0.969	0.015	0.9689	0.0072	0.975	0.013	0.9691	0.0083
15 GHz	0.9691	0.0079	0.9668	0.0081	0.970	0.020	0.9678	0.0088	0.961	0.018	0.9676	0.0089
18 GHz	0.971	0.013	0.977	0.010	0.969	0.019	0.976	0.012	0.977	0.018	0.974	0.012

Table 7. Calibration Factors and their LoP uncertainties of the comparison participants for 3.5 mm Standard power sensor

Labs	TÜBİTAK UME		SPARK		CMI		GUM		Trescal		Reference Value	
	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	y	$u(y)$ (k=1)
50 MHz			0.9945	0.0030	0.9900	0.0080	1.009	0.030	0.9830	0.0080	0.9929	0.0053
1 GHz	1.078	0.017	1.0763	0.0087	1.063	0.011	1.080	0.032	1.0550	0.0090	1.066	0.011
10 GHz	1.087	0.020	1.087	0.013	1.063	0.022	1.084	0.033	1.061	0.020	1.076	0.019
20 GHz	1.021	0.025	1.017	0.017	1.015	0.034	1.031	0.034	1.011	0.038	1.018	0.026
26.5 GHz	0.978	0.025			0.975	0.033	0.984	0.034	0.972	0.050	0.978	0.033

Table 8. Calibration Factors and their MCS uncertainties of the comparison participants for N Type Standard power sensor

Labs	TÜBİTAK UME		SPARK		CMI		GUM		Trescal		Reference Value	
	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	y	u(y) (k=1)
50 MHz			0.9982	0.0028	0.9980	0.0058	0.9994	0.0054	0.9970	0.0087	0.9983	0.0044
1 GHz	0.9932	0.0059	0.9925	0.0053	0.9920	0.0077	0.9924	0.0054	0.9930	0.0088	0.9926	0.0056
10 GHz	0.966	0.012	0.9685	0.0069	0.969	0.015	0.9689	0.0072	0.975	0.012	0.9691	0.0082
15 GHz	0.9691	0.0079	0.9668	0.0081	0.970	0.020	0.9678	0.0088	0.961	0.018	0.9676	0.0089
18 GHz	0.971	0.013	0.977	0.010	0.969	0.019	0.976	0.012	0.977	0.018	0.975	0.012

Table 9. Calibration Factors and their MCS uncertainties of the comparison participants for 3.5 mm Standard power sensor

Labs	TÜBİTAK UME		SPARK		CMI		GUM		Trescal		Reference Value	
	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	y	u(y) (k=1)
50 MHz			0.9945	0.0029	0.9900	0.0077	1.009	0.030	0.9830	0.0078	0.9929	0.0051
1 GHz	1.078	0.017	1.0763	0.0088	1.063	0.010	1.080	0.032	1.0550	0.0086	1.065	0.010
10 GHz	1.087	0.020	1.087	0.014	1.063	0.022	1.084	0.033	1.061	0.019	1.076	0.019
20 GHz	1.021	0.025	1.017	0.017	1.015	0.033	1.031	0.034	1.011	0.038	1.018	0.026
26.5 GHz	0.978	0.025			0.975	0.032	0.984	0.034	0.972	0.049	0.978	0.032

9. The Comparison Reference Value (CRV) and Reference Uncertainty

The comparison reference value (CRV) is calculated separately for each frequency level. The CRV (y) is determined as a weighted mean of the provided results where the weights are the inverse values of the squares of the associated standard uncertainties.

Comparison reference and associated uncertainty values was calculated using Eq. 1 and Eq. 2 respectively.

$$y = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i \cdot u^{-2}(x_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^N u^{-2}(x_i)} \quad (1)$$

$$u(y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N u^{-2}(x_i)}} \quad (2)$$

Where; x_i is the comparison participant's calibration factor value of the determined frequency, $u(x_i)$ is the uncertainty of the x_i values.

The expanded uncertainty of the Comparison Reference Values $U(y)$ was calculated Eq. 3.

$$U(y) = 2 \times u(y) \quad (3)$$

Degrees of equivalence, D , is calculated by subtracting the reference value from each measurement (Eq. 4) and its uncertainty (u_D) is calculated according to the Eq. 5.

$$D = x_{lab} - y \quad (4)$$

$$u_D = \sqrt{u(y)^2 + u_{lab}^2} \quad (5)$$

Where x_{lab} is participant laboratory calibration factor values and u_{lab} is uncertainty values for each calibration factor values. Degrees of equivalence with respect to the reference value and between each of the measurements can be found in Tables 10 to 11.

In this comparison, in order to calculate D and u_D values, participants' CF values and their LoP uncertainty values were used.

The E_n values which are calculated according to Eq. 6 stated at ISO / IEC 17043 "Conformity assessment — General requirements for proficiency testing" [3] given in Table 12 and 13.

$$E_n = \frac{D}{u_D} \quad (6)$$

where;

x_{lab} : Participant laboratory measurement result

y : CRV

u_{lab} : Participant laboratory measurement uncertainty

$u(y)$: Uncertainty of the CRV.

The laboratory measurement results can be utilized according to the criteria of E_n value which is given below.

- If $|E_n| < 1$ then it is successful
- If $|E_n| \geq 1$ then it is unsuccessful

Uncertainty budget provided by the participant and the full set of reported results can be found in Appendix 3.

10. Discussion of The Results

The comparison was organised to include five laboratories in a single loop.

The results were reported to the pilot laboratory in Calibration Factor.

All contributions to the measurement uncertainty listed in the report submitted by each participant. Participants were also requested to provide detailed uncertainty budgets and the combined standard uncertainties for the aforementioned measurand.

The CF measurement results and combined uncertainties of N Type and 3.5 mm power sensor with the reference values and combined uncertainties can be found in Table 6 and Table 7, respectively. Comparison reference values and combined uncertainties were calculated according to the Chapter 9.

Degree of equivalence values with respect to the reference value of CF and between each of the measurements can be found in Table 10 and Table 11.

The E_n value stated at ISO / IEC 17043 “Conformity assessment — General requirements for proficiency testing” [3] Standard for each CF measurement and frequencies can be found in Table 12 and Table 13.

DoE graphs, CF values of the participants with CRV are given in Appendix I for this comparison.

The reference values for the comparison were calculated using a weighted average of all participants’ results. The most of the measurements matched well with each power sensor

standards' reference values (CRV). The uncertainty evaluation also showed good agreement whether calculated using the GUM or MCS method.

Table 10. Degrees of Equivalence and uncertainty of N Type power sensor

Labs	TÜBİTAK UME		SPARK		CMI		GUM		Trescal	
	<i>D</i>	<i>U_D</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>U_D</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>U_D</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>U_D</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>U_D</i>
50 MHz			-0.0001	0.0052	-0.0003	0.0074	0.0011	0.0070	-0.0013	0.0100
1 GHz	-0.0006	0.0082	-0.0001	0.0078	-0.0006	0.0098	-0.0002	0.0078	0.0004	0.0106
10 GHz	0.0026	0.0142	-0.0006	0.0107	-0.0001	0.0171	-0.0002	0.0110	0.0059	0.0154
15 GHz	-0.0015	0.0119	-0.0008	0.0121	0.0024	0.0219	0.0002	0.0126	-0.0066	0.0201
18 GHz	0.0037	0.0173	0.0021	0.0157	-0.0055	0.0224	0.0015	0.0169	0.0025	0.0215

Table 11. Degrees of Equivalence and uncertainty of 3.5 mm power sensor

Labs	TÜBİTAK UME		SPARK		CMI		GUM		Trescal	
	<i>D</i>	<i>U_D</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>U_D</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>U_D</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>U_D</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>U_D</i>
50 MHz			-0.0035	0.0053	-0.0080	0.0091	0.0110	0.0303	-0.0150	0.0091
1 GHz	-0.0108	0.0201	0.0096	0.0135	-0.0037	0.0150	0.0133	0.0336	-0.0117	0.0136
10 GHz	-0.0090	0.0262	0.0084	0.0219	-0.0152	0.0279	0.0058	0.0372	-0.0172	0.0264
20 GHz	-0.0023	0.0338	-0.0017	0.0288	-0.0038	0.0411	0.0122	0.0411	-0.0078	0.0445
26.5 GHz	0.0000	0.0413			-0.0030	0.0464	0.0060	0.0471	-0.0060	0.0597

Table 12. En values of the comparison of N Type power sensor

Labs	$ E_n $				
	TÜBİTAK UME	SPARK	CMI	GUM	Trescal
50 MHz		0.02	0.04	0.16	0.13
1 GHz	0.07	0.01	0.06	0.03	0.03
10 GHz	0.19	0.05	0.00	0.01	0.39
15 GHz	0.12	0.06	0.11	0.02	0.33
18 GHz	0.21	0.13	0.24	0.09	0.12

Table 13. En values of the comparison of 3.5 mm power sensor

Labs	$ E_n $				
	TÜBİTAK UME	SPARK	CMI	GUM	Trescal
50 MHz		0.65	0.88	0.36	1.64
1 GHz	0.54	0.71	0.25	0.40	0.86
10 GHz	0.34	0.38	0.55	0.16	0.65
20 GHz	0.07	0.06	0.09	0.30	0.17
26.5 GHz	0.00		0.07	0.13	0.10

11. Summary and Conclusions

A comparison of power sensor calibration using Vector Network Analyser was planned among the partners of the EMP (European Partnership on Metrology) project. This inter-laboratory comparison was part of the project “Development of RF and Microwave Metrology Capability II” (22RPT04 ‘RFMicrowave2’).

5 (five) participants from the “22RPT04 RFMicrowave2” project were involved in the comparison. The procedure followed a technical protocol prepared by TÜBİTAK UME, which was agreed upon by all participants.

The comparison was carried out by measuring the Calibration Factors of the travelling standards, which was an Keysight- N type / N8481A and Keysight - 3.5 mm / U2063XA. Measurements were done at five different frequencies: 50 MHz, 1 GHz, 10 GHz, 15 GHz, 18 GHz for N type power sensor and 50 MHz, 1 GHz, 10 GHz, 20 GHz and 26.5 GHz for 3.5 mm power sensor.

The travelling standard is supplied by SPARK. CMI, GUM, TRESICAL and TUBİTAK was responsible for analysing the data and reporting the results respectively.

The reference values for the comparison were calculated using a weighted average of all participants' results. Most of the measurements matched well with these reference values.

The degrees of equivalence and E_n values are presented in the tables and graphs in the appendices. Results were considered satisfactory if $|E_n| < 1$.

References

- [1] Comparison protocol on Calibration Factor Calibration of RF power sensor with Vector Network Analyzer, EPM 22RPOT04 RFMicrowave 2 project, A.1.2.6, July 2025.
- [2] JCGM 100, "Evaluation of measurement data – Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement (GUM)", 2008.
- [3] ISO/IEC 17043:2023, Conformity assessment — General requirements for proficiency testing, International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, 2023.

Appendix I: Graphs of Degrees of Equivalence (DoE) according to the LoP (GUM) Uncertainty calculation

DoE graphs for N Type comparison standard (Model: N8481A SN:MY54350008)

DoE graphs for 3.5 mm comparison standard (Model: U2063XA SN:MY58000117)

CF graphs for N Type comparison standard (Model: N8481A SN:MY54350008) with CRV (Xref) and uncertainty of CRV

CF graphs for 3.5 mm comparison standard (Model: U2063XA SN:MY58000117) with CRV (Xref) and uncertainty of CRV

Appendix II: Comparison Reports of Participants

Appendix.II.A. Participant Report (TÜBİTAK UME)

1. PARTICIPANT INFORMATION

Laboratory Name	TÜBİTAK Ulusal Metroloji Enstitüsü
Related Person Name	Erkan Danacı
Telephone No	+902626765000/4500
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E-mail	erkan.danaci@tubitak.gov.tr
Adress	TÜBİTAK Ulusal Metroloji Enstitüsü (UME) TÜBİTAK Gebze Yerleşkesi Barış Mah. Dr. Zeki Acar Cad. No:1 41470 Gebze-Kocaeli, TÜRKİYE

2. MEASUREMENT DATE

10.01.2025, 13.03.2026

3. ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITION

Temperature : (23 ± 1) °C

Relative Humidity : (45 ± 15) rh%

4. TRAVELLING STANDARDS

Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No	Range	Pin Depth
Keysight	N8481A	MY54350008	10 MHz – 18 GHz	-0,000375
Keysight	U2063XA	MY58000117	10 MHz – 33 GHz	-0,0005

5. REFERENCES USED IN MEASUREMENT

Instrument Name	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No	Traceability
Power Sensor	Keysight	E4412A	MY60490005	TUBİTAK UME
Power Sensor	Keysight	E4413A	US38484022	TUBİTAK UME
PNA Network Analyzer	Keysight	N5225A	MY56051838	TUBİTAK UME
Calibration Kit	Agilent	85054B	MY39200345	TUBİTAK UME

6. MEASUREMENT METHOD

Before the measurement, the pin depth of the travelling standards was measured by TÜBİTAK UME's pin depth gauge kits (N Type and 3.5 mm).

SOL (Short, Open, Load) calibration method is applied to determine the error terms of the VNA, which was used in TÜBİTAK UME RF and Microwave Laboratory. The 50 MHz output power of the used VNA showed noticeable fluctuations and therefore could not be considered stable. Therefore, TÜBİTAK UME' report does not contain the 50 MHz reflection coefficient and CF values of travelling standards.

In order to measure Calibration Factor of travelling standards, a software developed by METU was used. Measurement setup is given in Figure 1. According to the software; Calibration Factor of the travelling standard was performed as direct comparison transfer method at 0 dBm for one orientation. VNA's receiver power sensors were used monitoring power sensor by developed software. Travelling standards and TÜBİTAK UME reference standards were connected to VNA's port-1 in a sequential order as determined by the software.

The declared final calibration factors are not relative calibration factor.

Measurements were performed by Mehmet Ali Kamalak, and Erkan Danacı.

The measurements and comparison report were done according to the technical protocol of the comparison.

Figure 1. TÜBİTAK UME Comparison Measurement Setup

7. MEASUREMENT RESULT

Pin depth of the travelling standards are given below.

N8481A : -0.000375"
 U2063XA : -0.0005"

Table 1. : Reflection Coefficient Values of the N8481A Power Sensor for UME

Frequency	Reflection Coefficient ($(S_{11} = x + jy)$) of the N8481A Power Sensor			
	Real Component x	Real Component Uncertainty (k=2)	Imaginary Component y	Imaginary Component Uncertainty (k=2)
50 MHz				
1 GHz	1.07E-02	4.01E-03	-1.56E-02	4.01E-03

10 GHz	-2.69E-02	4.02E-03	2.49E-02	4.02E-03
15 GHz	-5.59E-02	8.08E-03	-5.93E-02	8.08E-03
18 GHz	-1.19E-01	9.00E-03	-3.13E-03	9.00E-03

Table 2. : CF Values of the N8481A Power Sensor for UME

Frequency	Calibration Factor of the N8481A Power Sensor (k=2)	Uncertainty of CF of the First Power Sensor (k=2)
50 MHz		
1 GHz	0.993238	0.005936005
10 GHz	0.96642	0.011549548
15 GHz	0.96908	0.007865111
18 GHz	0.970809	0.012595103

Table 3. : Reflection Coefficient Values of the U2063XA Power Sensor for UME

Frequency	Reflection Coefficient ($(S_{11} = x + jy)$) of the U2063XA Power Sensor			
	Real Component x	Real Component Uncertainty (k=2)	Imaginary Component y	Imaginary Component Uncertainty (k=2)
50 MHz				
1 GHz	5.56E-03	8.01E-03	-1.76E-02	8.01E-03
10 GHz	-2.26E-02	8.01E-03	-9.19E-03	8.01E-03
20 GHz	1.43E-02	1.20E-02	-1.41E-02	1.20E-02
26.5 GHz	-9.92E-04	1.21E-02	-2.92E-02	1.21E-02

Table 4. : CF Values of the U2063XA Power Sensor for UME

Frequency	Calibration Factor of the U2063XA Power Sensor (k=2)	Uncertainty of CF of the Second Power Sensor (k=2)
50 MHz		
1 GHz	1.077523	0.017301602
10 GHz	1.087257	0.019824571
20 GHz	1.021101	0.024598171
26.5 GHz	0.978056	0.02526455

8. UNCERTAINTY BUDGET

8.1. Calibration Factor measurements uncertainty budget

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \frac{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT})\right)}{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD})\right)} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 1 GHz

Table 5: CF measurements uncertainty budget of the N8481A for UME

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
PSTD	0.966557872	0.001395262	Normal	-1,02972143	2,0642E-06
PR1S	0.899480715	1.50915E-05	Normal	1,106511058	2,78855E-10
PDUT	0.948409651	0.001395262	Normal	1,04942559	2,14395E-06
PR1D	0.899669692	1.29208E-05	Normal	-1,10627863	2,04318E-10
CFSTD	1.0141	0.0022	Normal	0,981446956	4,66207E-06
Γ_{DUT}	0.018902742	0.002002665	Normal	0,001588395	1,01189E-11
Γ_{STD}	0.01185116	0.002	Normal	0,03421512	4,6827E-09
Γ_{E11}	0.020066304	0.002003068	Normal	0,021703742	1,88999E-09
Θ_{DUT}	-0.96663627	0.105945713	Normal	0,000754431	6,3886E-09
Θ_{STD}	-2.03444394	0.168759847	Normal	-0,00024445	1,7018E-09
Θ_{E11}	2.576830815	0.099822443	Normal	0,000509984	2,59161E-09
CF DUT	0.995285358	Combined Uncertainty			0.002968003
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.005936005

Frequency : 10 GHz

Table 6: CF measurements uncertainty budget of the N8481A for UME

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
PSTD	0.824520602	0.001191347	Normal	-1.1760769	1.96313E-06
PR1S	0.79884736	3.75692E-05	Normal	1.213873486	2.07975E-09
PDUT	0.809545834	0.001191347	Normal	1.19783166	2.03642E-06
PR1D	0.798913958	3.55529E-05	Normal	-1.2137723	1.86219E-09
CFSTD	0.985	0.0055	Normal	0.984466629	2.93175E-05
ΓDUT	0.036658292	0.002007571	Normal	0.083182768	2.78874E-08
ΓSTD	0.025923734	0.002	Normal	-0.01463542	8.56782E-10
ΓE11	0.045911239	0.002015069	Normal	0.058154249	1.37323E-08
ΘDUT	2.394537377	0.05476443	Normal	-0.00114986	3.96537E-09
ΘSTD	0.62652743	0.077149379	Normal	-0.0022764	3.08435E-08
ΘE11	1.108245243	0.043890538	Normal	-0.00342626	2.26143E-08
CF DUT	Combined Uncertainty				
	Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)				

Frequency : 15 GHz

Table 7: CF measurements uncertainty budget of the N8481A for UME

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
PSTD	0.81068162	0.001170305	Normal	-1,1984383	1,96711E-06
PR1S	0.859658452	1.07304E-05	Normal	1,13016036	1,47066E-10
PDUT	0.802531452	0.001170305	Normal	1,210609134	2,00727E-06
PR1D	0.858164635	2.03322E-05	Normal	-1,13212764	5,29856E-10
CFSTD	0.982	0.006	Normal	0,989360393	3,5238E-05
ΓDUT	0.081503545	0.00404061	Normal	0,014514817	3,43967E-09
ΓSTD	0.046099458	0.004	Normal	-0,07450509	8,88161E-08
ΓE11	0.043043304	0.004014103	Normal	-0,05231093	4,40922E-08
ΘDUT	-2.32700537	0.04957588	Normal	0,006709152	1,10631E-07
ΘSTD	-1.39637545	0.086768917	Normal	-0,00173688	2,27126E-08
ΘE11	-2.21430492	0.093257316	Normal	0,004972273	2,15019E-07
CF DUT	Combined Uncertainty				0.006297552
	Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)				0.012595103

Frequency : 18 GHz

Table 8: CF measurements uncertainty budget of the N8481A for UME

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
PSTD	0.802016354	0.001157761	Normal	-1,2119346	1,96877E-06
PR1S	0.803442705	1.48582E-05	Normal	1,20978305	3,23106E-10
PDUT	0.799225267	0.001157761	Normal	1,216166963	1,98255E-06
PR1D	0.800952847	3.44264E-05	Normal	-1,2135438	1,7454E-09
CFSTD	0.983	0.005	Normal	0,988800982	2,44432E-05
Γ DUT	0.118968398	0.0045	Normal	-0,08412697	1,43316E-07
Γ STD	0.036155359	0.004	Normal	-0,01639362	4,30001E-09
Γ E11	0.044690041	0.004021481	Normal	-0,23721544	9,10035E-07
Θ DUT	-3.11524281	0.037825171	Normal	0,002785336	1,10998E-08
Θ STD	-1.62614141	0.110633668	Normal	-0,00308366	1,16388E-07
Θ E11	-2.89793787	0.089986065	Normal	-0,00029832	7,20638E-10
CF DUT	0.971991366	Combined Uncertainty			0.005437916
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.010875833

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \frac{(1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT}))}{(1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD}))} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 1 GHz

Table 9: CF measurements uncertainty budget of the U2063XA for UME

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
PSTD	0.975366231	0.001408014	Normal	-1,10551444	2,42294E-06
PR1S	0.89645432	9.72502E-06	Normal	1,20282922	1,36833E-10
PDUT	1.019676205	0.001408014	Normal	1,057474368	2,21694E-06
PR1D	0.896694662	1.19031E-05	Normal	-1,20250682	2,04878E-10
CFSTD	1.032	0.008	Normal	1,044846366	6,98691E-05
Γ_{DUT}	0.023770374	0.004005545	Normal	-0,0153004	3,75603E-09
Γ_{STD}	0.001552417	0.004	Normal	0,033382236	1,783E-08
Γ_{E11}	0.02261054	0.004003852	Normal	-0,01379326	3,04993E-09
Θ_{DUT}	-1.33430148	0.16850995	Normal	0,001100735	3,44046E-08
Θ_{STD}	2.880990262	2.576626506	Normal	5,51792E-05	2,02141E-08
Θ_{E11}	2.58546836	0.177079012	Normal	0,001155915	4,18973E-08
CF DUT	1.078281450	Combined Uncertainty			0.008650801
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.017301602

Frequency : 10 GHz

Table 10: CF measurements uncertainty budget of the U2063XA for UME

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
PSTD	0.836108834	0.001208094	Normal	-1,30624944	2,49031E-06
PR1S	0.797445368	2.51209E-05	Normal	1,369581843	1,18371E-09
PDUT	0.895222061	0.001208094	Normal	1,219995289	2,17229E-06
PR1D	0.798053039	6.39714E-05	Normal	-1,36853899	7,66454E-09
CFSTD	1.024	0.009	Normal	1,06656904	9,21431E-05
ΓDUT	0.030877025	0.004008835	Normal	-0,06829913	7,49664E-08
ΓSTD	0.00825409	0.004	Normal	-0,1546458	3,82645E-07
ΓE11	0.081059127	0.004037697	Normal	-0,04176377	2,84359E-08
ΘDUT	-2.80986966	0.129832296	Normal	0,005049716	4,29833E-07
ΘSTD	-0.3332443	0.484608243	Normal	0,000709964	1,18374E-07
ΘE11	-2.30043398	0.04981175	Normal	0,005759681	8,23115E-08
CF DUT	1.092166697	Combined Uncertainty			0.009912285
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.019824571

Frequency : 20 GHz

Table 11: CF measurements uncertainty budget of the U2063XA for UME

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
PSTD	0.791352085	0.001142334	Normal	-1,31025831	2,24027E-06
PR1S	0.833430379	2.38421E-05	Normal	1,244105896	8,79837E-10
PDUT	0.826859521	0.001142334	Normal	1,253992513	2,05199E-06
PR1D	0.830684675	3.95315E-05	Normal	-1,2482181	2,43482E-09
CFSTD	0.994	0.0115	Normal	1,043134455	0,000143905
ΓDUT	0.037502131	0.006007489	Normal	0,026506846	2,53572E-08
ΓSTD	0.04554119	0.006	Normal	-0,13450777	6,51324E-07
ΓE11	0.081986324	0.006044918	Normal	-0,06259069	1,43153E-07
ΘDUT	-0.83862902	0.160190592	Normal	0,006295053	1,01689E-06
ΘSTD	1.235157776	0.131748863	Normal	0,004698437	3,83178E-07
ΘE11	2.563006848	0.073730803	Normal	0,01099349	6,57006E-07
CF DUT	1.036875648	Combined Uncertainty			0.012299086
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.024598171

Frequency : 26.5 GHz

Table 12: CF measurements uncertainty budget of the U2063XA for UME

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
PSTD	0.709139987	0.001023677	Normal	-1,40233964	2,06078E-06
PR1S	0.827196561	3.34041E-05	Normal	1,202199282	1,61269E-09
PDUT	0.704850245	0.001023677	Normal	1,410874323	2,08594E-06
PR1D	0.823017052	5.31723E-05	Normal	-1,20830438	4,12785E-09
CFSTD	1.015	0.0125	Normal	0,979758731	0,000149989
Γ DUT	0.053299219	0.006026943	Normal	-0,20425425	1,51543E-06
Γ STD	0.043011626	0.006	Normal	-0,19671946	1,39315E-06
Γ E11	0.119537302	0.006090474	Normal	-0,16185589	9,7176E-07
Θ DUT	-1.64385709	0.113077511	Normal	0,006619815	5,6033E-07
Θ STD	1.547544704	0.139497166	Normal	0,005664905	6,24477E-07
Θ E11	2.186879395	0.050950405	Normal	0,01228472	3,91765E-07
CF DUT	0.994455112	Combined Uncertainty			0.012632275
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.02526455

Appendix.II.B. Participant Report (SPARK)

1. PARTICIPANT INFORMATION

Laboratory Name	SPARK CALIBRATION SERVICES
Related Person Name	SAMET AKLAR
Telephone No	+90 530 317 25 64
Fax No	-
E-mail	samet_aklar@sparkkalibrasyon.com.tr
Adress	M.Kemal Mah.Dumlupınar Bulv. No:274 B Blok. D:38, Mahall Ankara 06530 Çankaya-ANKARA/Türkiye

2. MEASUREMENT DATE

23/08/2025

3. ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITION

Temperature : (22 ± 3) °C

Relative Humidity : (40 ± 20) rh%

4. REFERENCES USED IN MEASUREMENT

Instrument Name	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No	Traceability
Network Analyzer	KEYSIGHT	N5231A / PNA	MY52251076	KEYSIGHT
PS (STD1)	KEYSIGHT	N8481A	MY54350008	KEYSIGHT
PS (STD2)	KEYSIGHT	N8485A	MY50310002	KEYSIGHT
PS (DUT1)	KEYSIGHT	N8481A	MY50360002	KEYSIGHT
PS (DUT2)	KEYSIGHT	U2063XA	MY58000117	KEYSIGHT
ADAPTER	KEYSIGHT	TYPE N – 2.4 FF		
ADAPTER	KEYSIGHT	3.5 – 2.4 FF		
NI MAX	NATIONAL INSTRUMENT	USB – GPIB		NATIONAL INSTRUMENT
POWER METER	KEYSGIHT	E4419B		KEYSIGHT

5. MEASUREMENT METHOD

Direct Measurement by using VBPSC software

Ripple Method for uncertainty calculation of reflection coefficient.

6. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

Frequency	Reflection Coefficient ($(S_{11} = x + jy)$) of the First Power Sensor			
	Real Component x	Real Component Uncertainty (k=2)	Imaginary Component y	Imaginary Component Uncertainty (k=2)
50 MHz	0.007921	0.000229	-0.02404	0.000287
1 GHz	0.006252	2.61E-05	-0.00634	9.34E-05
10 GHz	0.020417	0.000133	-0.01008	0.000105
15 GHz	0.039527	0.000222	-0.03845	0.00029
18 GHz	-0.02024	0.000345	0.060178	0.000337

Frequency	Calibration Factor of the First Power Sensor (k=2)	Uncertainty of CF of the First Power Sensor (k=2)
50 MHz	0.998176131	0.002749806
1 GHz	0.992520522	0.005324593
10 GHz	0.968505786	0.006847814
15 GHz	0.966840693	0.008087692
18 GHz	0.976579287	0.010286214

Frequency	Reflection Coefficient ($(S_{11} = x + jy)$) of the Second Power Sensor			
	Real Component x	Real Component Uncertainty (k=2)	Imaginary Component y	Imaginary Component Uncertainty (k=2)
50 MHz	-0.00307	0.000195	-0.00158	0.000182
1 GHz	0.004071	9.7E-05	0.003361	0.000134
10 GHz	0.005622	0.000118	-0.00887	9.17E-05
20 GHz	-0.02962	0.000375	0.046675	0.000363
26.5 GHz	-	-	-	-

Frequency	Calibration Factor of the Second Power Sensor (k=2)	Uncertainty of CF of the Second Power Sensor (k=2)
50 MHz	0.994545917	0.002988424
1 GHz	1.076323229	0.008746985
10 GHz	1.086633885	0.013490806
20 GHz	1.017064024	0.017193573
26.5 GHz	-	

7. UNCERTAINTY BUDGET

7.1. Calibration Factor measurements uncertainty budget

Model: N8481A SN:MY54350008 Power Sensor

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \frac{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT})\right)}{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD})\right)}$$

Frequency : 50 MHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CFSTD	1	0.002	Normal	0,998176131	3,98542E-06
PDT	1.013846829	0.000878481	Normal	0,984543328	7,48057E-07
PSTD	1.015509837	0.000881847	Normal	-0,98293103	7,51333E-07
PMD	1.018118515	8.94141E-06	Normal	-0,98041251	7,68475E-11
PMS	1.017547696	1.09484E-05	Normal	0,9809625	1,15347E-10
GDT	0.02531353	0.010517649	Normal	-0,0040826	1,84379E-09
TDT	-1.25252069	0.52164233	Normal	0,001037483	2,92892E-07
GSTD	0.022999911	0.0045	Normal	0,02074159	8,71182E-09
TSTD	-1.68075735	0.195652933	Normal	-0,00081864	2,56542E-08
GE11	0.020630636	0.013003944	Normal	0,018114306	5,54873E-08
TE11	2.723513544	0.521374041	Normal	0,00021884	1,30182E-08
Measured Value	0.998176131	Combined Uncertainty			0.00242541
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.004850819

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \left(\frac{1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT})}{1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD})} \right)$$

Frequency : 1 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CFSTD	0.9898	0.0023	Normal	1,0027	5,3186E-06
PDT	1.023666602	0.000888315	Normal	0,9696	7,41855E-07
PSTD	1.02075458	0.000884836	Normal	-0,972	7,39704E-07
PMD	1.026809238	1.49568E-05	Normal	-0,967	2,09185E-10
PMS	1.026348853	1.60803E-05	Normal	0,967	2,41792E-10
GDT	0.008903288	0.011647867	Normal	0,01	1,35673E-08
TDT	-0.792284769	1.311621575	Normal	-3E-04	1,54832E-07
GSTD	0.006999719	0.0045	Normal	0,0362	2,65364E-08
TSTD	1.03143036	0.642882983	Normal	7E-06	2,02516E-11
GE11	0.018221566	0.011088111	Normal	0,0188	4,34541E-08
TE11	-1.057845037	0.670232879	Normal	-3E-04	4,04291E-08
Measured Value	0.992520522	Combined Uncertainty			0.002660724
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.005321449

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \left(\frac{1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT})}{1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD})} \right)$$

Frequency : 10 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CFSTD	0.9646	0.00305	Normal	1,004049125	9,37799E-06
PDT	0.9934	0.00086259	Normal	0,974938016	7,07234E-07
PSTD	0.9878	0.000856693	Normal	-0,98045936	7,0552E-07
PMD	1.022	2.20181E-05	Normal	-0,94767277	4,35388E-10
PMS	1.0217	1.63033E-05	Normal	0,94793705	2,38842E-10
GDT	0.0228	0.014349295	Normal	0,019362974	7,71979E-08
TDT	-0.459	0.379546423	Normal	0,001376915	2,73114E-07
GSTD	0.034	0.0045	Normal	-0,0507592	5,21741E-08
TSTD	0.1588	0.132353438	Normal	-0,00129472	2,93645E-08
GE11	0.0328	0.011703539	Normal	-0,03918826	2,10352E-07
TE11	2.3385	0.366738449	Normal	8,21933E-05	9,08627E-10
Measured Value	0.968505786	Combined Uncertainty			0.003381498
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.006762995

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \left(\frac{1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT})}{1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD})} \right)$$

Frequency : 15 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CFSTD	0.9599	0.00345	Normal	1,007230642	1,20752E-05
PDT	1.001852749	0.000868749	Normal	0,965052693	7,02895E-07
PSTD	0.996119608	0.000863828	Normal	-0,97060703	7,02977E-07
PMD	0.988619979	1.13827E-05	Normal	-0,97797001	1,2392E-10
PMS	0.988237363	8.53822E-06	Normal	0,978348653	6,97786E-11
GDT	0.055146049	0.009147598	Normal	-0,14005206	1,64132E-06
TDT	-0.771646742	0.165929376	Normal	0,004753835	6,22207E-07
GSTD	0.071999349	0.0045	Normal	0,132162284	3,53704E-07
TSTD	-0.685914207	0.062500565	Normal	-0,00706514	1,94989E-07
GE11	0.084709561	0.010200514	Normal	0,021157951	4,65791E-08
TE11	1.320949241	0.107740955	Normal	-0,00231131	6,20123E-08
Measured Value	0.966840693	Combined Uncertainty			0.004049954
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.008099907

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \frac{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT})\right)}{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD})\right)}$$

Frequency : 18 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CFSTD	0.9695	0.00425	Normal	1,007301998	1,83272E-05
PDT	0.996859287	0.000864119	Normal	0,979656106	7,16629E-07
PSTD	0.987970505	0.000856568	Normal	-0,98847008	7,16887E-07
PMD	1.049042981	1.45764E-05	Normal	-0,930924	1,84132E-10
PMS	1.048525931	1.54587E-05	Normal	0,931383057	2,07302E-10
GDT	0.063489588	0.014684459	Normal	-0,03851395	3,19854E-07
TDT	1.895221982	0.392711417	Normal	0,005519221	4,69789E-06
GSTD	0.039000123	0.0045	Normal	0,033034253	2,20981E-08
TSTD	1.958263933	0.115384252	Normal	-0,00347481	1,60752E-07
GE11	0.048619428	0.020923189	Normal	-0,02379491	2,4787E-07
TE11	-0.744298727	0.409045089	Normal	0,002044412	6,99325E-07
Measured Value	0.976579287	Combined Uncertainty			0.005090083
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.010180165

Model: U2063XA SN:MY58000117 Power Sensor

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \frac{(1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT}))}{(1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD}))}$$

Frequency : 50 MHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CFSTD	1	0.003	Normal	0,995837954	8,92524E-06
PDT	0.980386557	0.000849691	Normal	1,015760515	7,44912E-07
PSTD	0.984326847	0.000853074	Normal	-1,0116944	7,44856E-07
PMD	1.005495728	1.08218E-05	Normal	-0,99039501	1,14872E-10
PMS	1.00534533	6.62909E-06	Normal	0,990543174	4,31176E-11
GDT	0.00345012	0.012858965	Normal	-0,043049	3,06435E-07
TDT	-2.664641536	3.16617804	Normal	1,51288E-05	2,29446E-09
GSTD	0.023000421	0.005	Normal	0,006010338	9,03104E-10
TSTD	-1.335192158	0.217387321	Normal	-0,00098562	4,59079E-08
GE11	0.021724685	0.013097896	Normal	-0,00047338	3,84435E-11
TE11	2.766144935	0.489920743	Normal	-0,00097049	2,26065E-07
Measured Value	0.995837954	Combined Uncertainty			0.003316144
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.006632287

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \left(\frac{1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT})}{1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD})} \right)$$

Frequency : 1 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CFSTD	0.9879	0.0038	Normal	1,087151638	1,70666E-05
PDT	1.070502065	0.000927694	Normal	1,003264859	8,66245E-07
PSTD	0.98424093	0.000853202	Normal	-1,0911933	8,66776E-07
PMD	1.012434236	1.22583E-05	Normal	-1,06080678	1,69096E-10
PMS	1.012023684	1.1163E-05	Normal	1,061237124	1,40342E-10
GDT	0.005279097	0.011866535	Normal	-0,02744083	1,06033E-07
TDT	0.690069314	2.169950155	Normal	0,00014332	9,67193E-08
GSTD	0.006000199	0.005	Normal	0,015973952	6,37918E-09
TSTD	1.054130828	0.833305731	Normal	-0,00021085	3,08714E-08
GE11	0.017969583	0.01268836	Normal	-0,00272772	1,19787E-09
TE11	0.089910207	0.586644449	Normal	-6,7526E-05	1,56925E-09
Measured Value	1.073997103	Combined Uncertainty			0.004363796
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.008727593

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \left(\frac{1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT})}{1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD})} \right)$$

Frequency : 10 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CFSTD	0.9676	0.00585	Normal	1,124248693	4,3255E-05
PDT	1.0689	0.000926048	Normal	1,017717453	8,88222E-07
PSTD	0.9498	0.000823391	Normal	-1,14526248	8,89247E-07
PMD	1.0031	1.15734E-05	Normal	-1,08444168	1,5752E-10
PMS	1.0025	8.26296E-06	Normal	1,085078584	8,03885E-11
GDT	0.0105	0.009695306	Normal	0,022734514	4,85841E-08
TDT	-1.006	1.29782129	Normal	-0,00010937	2,01477E-08
GSTD	0.026	0.005	Normal	-0,02463918	1,51772E-08
TSTD	-1.606	0.192308986	Normal	-0,00011003	4,47735E-10
GE11	0.0115	0.006030527	Normal	-0,03495385	4,44325E-08
TE11	-1.706	1.357808992	Normal	-0,0002194	8,87464E-08
Measured Value	1.087823035	Combined Uncertainty			0.006726831
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.013453663

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \left(\frac{1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT})}{1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD})} \right)$$

Frequency : 20 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CFSTD	0.966	0.00795	Normal	1,060874934	7,11316E-05
PDT	1.017024044	0.00088	Normal	1,007650893	7,86295E-07
PSTD	0.964482753	0.00084	Normal	-1,06254382	7,96622E-07
PMD	0.985297108	1.2E-05	Normal	-1,04009763	1,5578E-10
PMS	0.985085576	1E-05	Normal	1,040320975	1,08227E-10
GDT	0.055281137	0.01456	Normal	0,077586318	1,27612E-06
TDT	2.136284841	0.17202	Normal	0,004946351	7,23982E-07
GSTD	0.018000466	0.005	Normal	0,118526976	3,51216E-07
TSTD	-0.078523084	0.27777	Normal	-0,00014528	1,62848E-09
GE11	0.057902666	0.00406	Normal	0,110920637	2,02804E-07
TE11	0.146440365	0.29211	Normal	0,004801071	1,96684E-06
Measured Value	1.024805186	Combined Uncertainty			0.00878848
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.017576961

Appendix.II.C. Participant Report (CMI)

1. PARTICIPANT INFORMATION

Laboratory Name:	Czech Metrology Institute Department of Primary Metrology of RF Electrical Quantities
Name of contact person:	Jan Grajciar
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2. TRAVELLING STANDARDS

The travelling standards are two coaxial power sensors.

Manufacturer:	Keysight
Model:	N8481A
Serial number:	MY54350008
Frequency Range:	10 MHz – 18 GHz
Manufacturer:	Keysight
Model:	U2063XA
Serial number:	MY58000117
Frequency Range:	10 MHz – 33 GHz

3. MEASUREMENT DATE

10th – 12th November 2025

4. ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS

Temperature: (23 ± 2) °C

Relative Humidity: (33 ± 20) %

5. STANDARDS USED IN MEASUREMENT

Instrument Name	Manufacturer	Model	Serial Number	Traceability
Network Analyzer	Agilent	E8364B	MY43040291	calibrated at CMI 1013-KL-70009-23
Calibration Kit	Hewlett-Packard	85054D	3101A00569	calibrated at CMI 1013-KL-70130-24
Calibration Kit	Hewlett-Packard	85052C	3101A00651	calibrated at CMI 1013-KL-70046-23
Power Meter	Rohde & Schwarz	NRVD	835843/022	calibrated at CMI 1013-KL-10048-24
Power Meter	Keysight	N1913A	MY64270010	calibrated at Keysight Technologies EQ671092-6515039-1
Power Sensor	Rohde & Schwarz	NRV-Z51	836942/010	calibrated at CMI 1013-KL-10018-24
Power Sensor	Rohde & Schwarz	NRV-Z55	100290	calibrated at CMI 1013-KL-10038-24

6. SOFTWARE

The calibration factor was measured using the VBpsc program.

7. DESCRIPTION OF MEASUREMENT METHOD

Calibration of RF power sensors using vector network analyzer (VNA).

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \frac{(1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT}))}{(1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD}))} \quad (1)$$

In Equation (1):

CF_{DUT} : Calculated calibration factor values of the DUT Power Sensor (PS),

CF_{STD} : Known calibration factor values of the STD PS,

P_{STD} : Power values read from the power meter connected to the STD PS,

P_{R1S} : Power values read from R1 inside the port of the VNA used, measured from the STD PS (taken as the applied power value to the STD PS),

P_{DUT} : Power values read from the power meter connected to the DUT PS,

P_{R1D} : Power values read from R1 inside the port of the VNA used, measured from the DUT PS (taken as the applied power value to the DUT PS),

Γ_{STD} : Reflection coefficients of the STD PS,

Γ_{e11} : Source impedance match error terms of the VNA port used,

Γ_{DUT} : Reflection coefficients of the DUT PS,

Θ_{STD} : Phases of the reflection coefficients of the STD PS,

Θ_{e11} : Phases of the source impedance match error term of the VNA port used,

Θ_{DUT} : Phases of the reflection coefficients of the DUT PS.

[1] USER MANUAL, VNA-BASED POWER SENSOR CALIBRATION SOFTWARE, Version 5 - 15.10.2025

8. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

8.1. Measurement of Calibration Factor (CF)

Keysight N8481A (MY54350008)

Frequency (GHz)	Calibration Factor of Travelling Standard @1 mW	
	CF (1)	Uncertainty (k = 2)
0.05	0.998	0.006
1	0.992	0.008
10	0.969	0.015
15	0.970	0.020
18	0.969	0.019

Keysight U2063XA (MY58000117)

Frequency (GHz)	Calibration Factor of Travelling Standard @1 mW	
	CF* (1)	Uncertainty (k = 2)
0.05	0.990	0.008
1	1.063	0.011

10	1.063	0.022
20	1.015	0.034
26.5	0.975	0.033

**data valid for autocalibration using built-in DC reference source!!!*

8.2. Measurement of Complex Reflection Coefficient

Keysight N8481A (MY54350008)

Frequency (GHz)	Reflection Coefficient of Travelling standard ($S_{11} = x + jy$)			
	Real Component x	Real Component Uncertainty (k = 2)	Imaginary Component y	Imaginary Component Uncertainty (k = 2)
0.05	0.008 5	0.002 3	-0.024 2	0.002 3
1	0.006 2	0.002 2	-0.006 7	0.002 2
10	0.011 1	0.002 8	-0.001 2	0.002 8
15	0.042 4	0.002 9	-0.026 7	0.002 9
18	-0.010 2	0.007 1	0.026 3	0.007 1

Keysight U2063XA (MY58000117)

Frequency (GHz)	Reflection Coefficient of Travelling standard ($S_{11} = x + jy$)			
	Real Component x	Real Component Uncertainty (k = 2)	Imaginary Component y	Imaginary Component Uncertainty (k = 2)
0.05	-0.003 5	0.002 5	-0.001 1	0.002 5
1	0.005 0	0.001 5	0.003 5	0.001 5
10	0.009 4	0.002 4	-0.002 5	0.002 4
20	-0.035 4	0.003 0	0.046 7	0.003 0
26.5	0.015 2	0.004 4	0.064 7	0.004 4

9. UNCERTAINTY BUDGET

9.1. Calibration Factor (CF) measurement uncertainty budget

i. Keysight N8481A (MY54350008)

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \frac{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT})\right)}{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD})\right)} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 0.05 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF STD	0.99300	2.5E-03	1.0E+00	2.5E-03
Pow DUT	0.93679	1.4E-03	1.1E+00	1.5E-03
Pow STD	0.93310	3.9E-05	-1.1E+00	4.2E-05
PM(R1) DUT	1.02662	2.5E-05	-9.7E-01	2.5E-05

PM(R1) STD	1.02700	7.1E-05	9.7E-01	6.9E-05
 RC_DUT 	0.02585	1.2E-03	1.1E-02	1.3E-05
Phase RC_DUT	-1.23992	4.6E-02	-1.2E-03	5.6E-05
 RC_STD 	0.01718	1.2E-03	3.8E-02	4.4E-05
Phase RC_STD	-0.11843	6.8E-02	5.2E-04	3.5E-05
 E11 	0.02431	1.7E-03	3.8E-02	6.3E-05
Phase E11	-0.55563	6.8E-02	-7.0E-04	4.8E-05
CF DUT	0.998	Combined Uncertainty		2.9E-03
		Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)		5.8E-03

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \frac{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT})\right)}{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD})\right)} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 1 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF STD	0.97909	3.5E-03	1.0E+00	3.5E-03
Pow DUT	0.91852	1.4E-03	1.1E+00	1.5E-03
Pow STD	0.90627	5.1E-05	-1.1E+00	5.6E-05
PM(R1) DUT	1.01327	6.5E-05	-9.8E-01	6.3E-05
PM(R1) STD	1.01337	2.9E-05	9.8E-01	2.8E-05
RC_DUT	0.00910	1.1E-03	1.4E-02	1.6E-05
Phase RC_DUT	-0.83407	1.3E-01	-9.0E-05	1.1E-05
RC_STD	0.01378	1.1E-03	-1.7E-02	1.9E-05
Phase RC_STD	-1.32001	8.1E-02	2.9E-05	2.3E-06
E11	0.00871	1.7E-03	-1.2E-02	2.1E-05
Phase E11	-1.69996	1.9E-01	-6.1E-05	1.2E-05
CF DUT	0.992	Combined Uncertainty		3.8E-03
		Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)		7.7E-03

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \frac{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT})\right)}{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD})\right)} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 10 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF STD	0.95303	7.0E-03	1.0E+00	7.1E-03
Pow DUT	0.81032	1.2E-03	1.2E+00	1.4E-03
Pow STD	0.79543	5.0E-05	-1.2E+00	6.1E-05
PM(R1) DUT	1.02534	6.6E-05	-9.5E-01	6.3E-05
PM(R1) STD	1.02573	2.3E-05	9.5E-01	2.2E-05
RC_DUT	0.01139	1.5E-03	9.3E-02	1.4E-04
Phase RC_DUT	-0.14759	1.3E-01	-9.5E-04	1.2E-04
RC_STD	0.02385	1.4E-03	-1.2E-01	1.7E-04
Phase RC_STD	-1.13903	6.0E-02	-7.8E-04	4.7E-05
E11	0.06449	2.7E-03	-2.8E-02	7.7E-05
Phase E11	-2.26751	4.6E-02	-1.7E-03	7.9E-05
CF DUT	0.969	Combined Uncertainty		7.3E-03
		Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)		1.5E-02

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \frac{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT})\right)}{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD})\right)} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 15 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF STD	0.94314	9.5E-03	1.0E+00	9.8E-03
Pow DUT	0.81408	1.2E-03	1.2E+00	1.4E-03
Pow STD	0.79073	5.0E-05	-1.2E+00	6.1E-05
PM(R1) DUT	1.05400	1.3E-05	-9.2E-01	1.2E-05
PM(R1) STD	1.05411	3.8E-05	9.2E-01	3.5E-05
RC_DUT	0.05082	1.5E-03	-8.2E-02	1.3E-04
Phase RC_DUT	-0.57267	3.0E-02	-3.5E-03	1.1E-04
RC_STD	0.02892	1.5E-03	1.0E-01	1.5E-04
Phase RC_STD	0.47092	5.1E-02	-1.1E-03	5.4E-05
E11	0.05485	3.3E-03	-2.3E-02	7.5E-05
Phase E11	-0.12193	6.9E-02	-4.5E-03	3.1E-04
CF DUT	0.970	Combined Uncertainty		9.9E-03
		Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)		2.0E-02

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \frac{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT})\right)}{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD})\right)} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 18 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF STD	0.93362	9.0E-03	1.0E+00	9.3E-03
Pow DUT	0.73141	1.1E-03	1.3E+00	1.5E-03
Pow STD	0.70680	3.5E-05	-1.4E+00	4.8E-05
PM(R1) DUT	1.07589	3.1E-05	-9.0E-01	2.8E-05
PM(R1) STD	1.07625	6.6E-05	9.0E-01	5.9E-05
RC_DUT	0.03002	3.6E-03	-2.7E-03	9.6E-06
Phase RC_DUT	1.93587	1.2E-01	4.0E-03	4.7E-04
RC_STD	0.03422	3.5E-03	8.7E-02	3.1E-04
Phase RC_STD	1.23454	1.0E-01	-3.4E-03	3.5E-04
E11	0.06792	5.8E-03	4.3E-02	2.5E-04
Phase E11	-0.38756	6.5E-02	5.7E-04	3.7E-05
CF DUT	0.969	Combined Uncertainty		9.5E-03
		Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)		1.9E-02

ii. Keysight U2063XA (MY58000117)

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \frac{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT})\right)}{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD})\right)} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 0.05 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF STD	1.00490	3.3E-03	9.9E-01	3.3E-03
Pow DUT	0.91802	1.4E-03	1.1E+00	1.5E-03
Pow STD	0.93110	1.3E-03	-1.1E+00	1.4E-03
PM(R1) DUT	1.02045	2.6E-05	-9.7E-01	2.5E-05
PM(R1) STD	1.01948	4.0E-05	9.7E-01	3.9E-05
RC_DUT	0.00364	1.3E-03	5.9E-02	7.4E-05
Phase RC_DUT	-2.73445	3.4E-01	-4.5E-05	1.5E-05
RC_STD	0.00164	1.3E-03	2.7E-02	3.3E-05
Phase RC_STD	-0.91510	7.6E-01	8.9E-05	6.8E-05
E11	0.03050	3.4E-03	8.5E-03	2.9E-05
Phase E11	-0.20134	6.4E-02	4.4E-05	2.8E-06
CF DUT	0.990	Combined Uncertainty		3.8E-03
		Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)		7.7E-03

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \frac{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT})\right)}{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD})\right)} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 1 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF STD	0.98610	4.4E-03	1.1E+00	4.7E-03
Pow DUT	0.95376	1.4E-03	1.1E+00	1.6E-03
Pow STD	0.88390	1.3E-03	-1.2E+00	1.5E-03
PM(R1) DUT	1.01026	2.7E-05	-1.1E+00	2.9E-05
PM(R1) STD	1.00946	4.4E-05	1.1E+00	4.6E-05
RC_DUT	0.00596	7.5E-04	-3.7E-02	2.8E-05
Phase RC_DUT	0.52115	1.3E-01	1.0E-04	1.3E-05
RC_STD	0.00201	7.5E-04	-4.1E-02	3.1E-05
Phase RC_STD	-3.04192	3.7E-01	1.4E-06	5.1E-07
E11	0.01921	2.9E-03	-1.6E-02	4.6E-05
Phase E11	-0.08286	9.7E-02	1.0E-04	1.0E-05
CF DUT	1.063	Combined Uncertainty		5.2E-03
		Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)		1.0E-02

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \frac{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT})\right)}{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD})\right)} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 10 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF STD	0.94570	9.5E-03	1.1E+00	1.1E-02
Pow DUT	0.82163	1.2E-03	1.3E+00	1.6E-03
Pow STD	0.73220	1.1E-03	-1.5E+00	1.5E-03
PM(R1) DUT	1.02143	3.6E-05	-1.0E+00	3.8E-05
PM(R1) STD	1.02118	2.4E-05	1.0E+00	2.5E-05
RC_DUT	0.01043	1.2E-03	4.3E-02	5.1E-05
Phase RC_DUT	-0.25793	1.2E-01	6.8E-04	7.8E-05
RC_STD	0.04915	1.2E-03	3.4E-02	4.1E-05
Phase RC_STD	-1.28830	2.4E-02	-3.5E-03	8.4E-05
E11	0.03663	3.0E-03	5.8E-02	1.7E-04
Phase E11	2.40794	8.3E-02	-2.8E-03	2.3E-04
CF DUT	1.063	Combined Uncertainty		1.1E-02
		Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)		2.2E-02

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \frac{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT})\right)}{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD})\right)} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 20 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF STD	0.93340	1.5E-02	1.1E+00	1.6E-02
Pow DUT	0.67374	1.0E-03	1.5E+00	1.5E-03
Pow STD	0.61307	8.9E-04	-1.7E+00	1.5E-03
PM(R1) DUT	1.03599	5.1E-05	-9.8E-01	5.0E-05
PM(R1) STD	1.03580	3.7E-05	9.8E-01	3.6E-05
RC_DUT	0.05801	1.5E-03	-1.3E-01	2.0E-04
Phase RC_DUT	2.20906	2.6E-02	-2.6E-03	6.6E-05
RC_STD	0.03611	1.5E-03	-8.1E-02	1.2E-04
Phase RC_STD	-1.55141	4.2E-02	-4.0E-03	1.7E-04
E11	0.06790	3.8E-03	-1.6E-01	5.9E-04
Phase E11	-2.53254	5.4E-02	-6.6E-03	3.5E-04
CF DUT	1.015	Combined Uncertainty		1.7E-02
		Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)		3.3E-02

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \frac{(1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT}))}{(1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD}))} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 26.5 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF STD	0.92050	1.5E-02	1.1E+00	1.6E-02
Pow DUT	0.64625	9.8E-04	1.5E+00	1.5E-03
Pow STD	0.60413	8.7E-04	-1.6E+00	1.4E-03
PM(R1) DUT	1.01434	6.2E-05	-9.6E-01	5.9E-05
PM(R1) STD	1.01419	5.4E-05	9.6E-01	5.2E-05
 RC_DUT 	0.06594	2.2E-03	-8.1E-02	1.8E-04
Phase RC_DUT	1.33981	3.3E-02	-3.1E-03	1.0E-04
 RC_STD 	0.06704	2.2E-03	-6.4E-02	1.4E-04
Phase RC_STD	-0.46898	3.3E-02	4.5E-03	1.5E-04
 E11 	0.04770	4.1E-03	-2.0E-01	8.2E-04
Phase E11	-1.86242	1.0E-01	1.4E-03	1.5E-04
CF DUT	0.975	Combined Uncertainty		1.6E-02
		Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)		3.2E-02

Appendix.II.D. Participant Report (GUM)

1. PARTICIPANT INFORMATION

Laboratory Name:	Microwave, Electromagnetic Field and Electromagnetic Compatibility Laboratory, Electricity and Radiation Department, Central Office of Measures
Name of contact person:	Łukasz Usydus
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2. TRAVELLING STANDARDS

The travelling standards are two coaxial power sensors

Manufacturer	Keysight
Model	N8481A
Serial number	MY54350008
Frequency range	10 MHz – 18 GHz

Manufacturer	Keysight
Model	U2063XA
Serial number	MY58000117
Frequency range	10 MHz – 18 GHz

3. MEASUREMENT DATE

26 – 28 November 2025

4. ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS

Temperature: (23 ± 1) °C

Relative humidity: (45 ± 5) %

5. STANDARDS USED IN MEASUREMENTS

Instrument name	Manufacturer	Model	Serial number	Traceability
Vector Network Analyzer	Agilent	E8364B	MY43030326	GUM: Z4-Z44.4180.97.2023.2801.1
Calibration kit type N	Agilent	85054B	MY39200148	NPL: 2021030417-1
Calibration kit 3.5 mm	Agilent	85052C	MY44300101	NPL: 2021030417-2
Power meter	Keysight	N1914A	MY55136013	GUM: L5-L54.4180.100.2021.3529
Standard power sensor	Hewlett-Packard	8481A	3318A86618	GUM: L5-L54.4180.86.2020.3343.2
Standard power sensor	Agilent	8485A	MY41092842	METAS: 217-04178

6. SOFTWARE

The calibration factor was measured using the VBPSC software.

7. DESCRIPTION OF MEASUREMENT METHOD

Calibration of was performed according to VBPSC software's built-in procedures. The model function is stated below:

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \frac{(1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT}))}{(1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD}))} \quad (1)$$

where:

CF_{DUT} : Calculated calibration factor values of the DUT Power Sensor (PS),

CF_{STD} : Known calibration factor values of the STD PS,

P_{STD} : Power values read from the power meter connected to the STD PS,

P_{R1S} : Power values from R1 inside the port of the VNA used, measured from the STD PS (taken as the applied power value to the STD PS),

P_{DUT} : Power values read from the power meter connected to the DUT PS,

P_{R1D} : Power values read from R1 inside the port of the VNA used, measured from the DUT PS (taken as the applied power value to the DUT PS),

Γ_{STD} : Reflection coefficients of the STD PS,

Γ_{e11} : Source impedance match error terms of the VNA port used,

Γ_{DUT} : Reflection coefficients of the DUT PS,

Θ_{STD} : Phases of the reflection coefficients of the STD PS,

Θ_{e11} : Phases of the source impedance match error term of the VNA port used,

Θ_{DUT} : Phases of the reflection coefficients of the DUT PS.

The measurement setup is shown on Fig.1. In case of N8481A calibration both DUT and standard power sensors were connected to N1914A power meter's channel A. The measurements were performed on VNA's port 1, which had been pre-calibrated at 0 dBm using 85054B calibration kit. The standard power sensor used was type-N 8481A with serial number 3318A86618. Each power sensor was zero'ed and calibrated with N1914A power meter's 0 dBm 50 MHz reference source.

Connection diagram for UX2063XA calibration was different in a way that DUT was connected directly to PC via USB interface, while standard power sensor (8485A ser. no. MY41092842) was connected to the N1914A power meter. The VNA had been pre-calibrated at 0 dBm using Agilent 85052C TRL calibration kit. The standard power sensor used was 3.5 mm 8485A with serial number MY41092842. The standard sensor was zero'ed

and calibrated with N1914A power meter's 0 dBm 50 MHz reference source while the DUT was autocalibrated with its internal DC source.

The environmental conditions were controlled by air conditioning combined with humidifier and monitored with laboratory grade thermo-hygrometer.

Fig.1. Power sensor calibration setup: A. Connection schematics for N8481A power sensor calibration; B. Connection schematics for U2063XA power sensor calibration.

8. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

8.1. Measurements of Calibration Factor (CF)

Keysight N8481A (MY54350008)

Frequency GHz	Calibration factor of travelling standard @ 1 mW	
	CF	Uncertainty (k=2)
0.05	0.9994	0.0054
1	0.9924	0.0054
10	0.9689	0.0072
15	0.9678	0.0088
18	0.976	0.012

Keysight U2063XA (MY58000117)

Frequency GHz	Calibration factor of travelling standard @ 1 mW	
	CF	Uncertainty (k=2)
0.05	1.009	0.030
1	1.080	0.032
10	1.084	0.033
20	1.031	0.034
26.5	0.984	0.034

8.2. Measurement of complex reflection coefficient

Keysight N8481A (MY54350008)

Frequency GHz	Reflection coefficient of travelling standard ($S_{11} = x + jy$)			
	Real component x	Real component uncertainty (k = 2)	Imaginary component y	Imaginary component uncertainty (k = 2)
0.05	0.0087	0.0063	-0.0239	0.0063
1	0.0072	0.0062	-0.0055	0.0062
10	0.010	0.012	0.006	0.012
15	0.042	0.012	-0.012	0.012
18	-0.014	0.012	0.018	0.012

Keysight U2063XA (MY58000117)

Frequency GHz	Reflection coefficient of travelling standard ($S_{11} = x + jy$)			
	Real component x	Real component uncertainty (k = 2)	Imaginary component y	Imaginary component uncertainty (k = 2)
0.05	-0.0046	0.0057	-0.0014	0.0057
1	0.0032	0.0057	0.0034	0.0057
10	0.0033	0.0061	-0.0022	0.0061
20	-0.0327	0.0052	0.0508	0.0052
26.5	0.0031	0.0056	0.0452	0.0056

9. UNCERTAINTY BUDGET

9.1. Calibration factor (CF) measurement budget for Keysight N8481A (MY54350008)

Model function (applicable to all frequencies):

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \frac{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT})\right)}{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD})\right)} \quad (1)$$

Frequency: 50 MHz

Definition	Expected Value xi	Standard Uncertainty u(xi)	Sensitivity Coefficient ci	Uncertainty contribution u(yi)
CF STD	1.0000	0.0018	0.9994	0.0017
Pow DUT	0.9228	0.0013	1.0831	0.0014
Pow STD	0.9275	0.0013	-1.0776	-0.0014
PM(R1) DUT	1.07823	0.00020	-0.92693	-0.00018
PM(R1) STD	1.08410	0.00016	0.92191	0.00015
RC_DUT	0.0254	0.0031	-0.0226	-0.000071
Phase RC_DUT	-1.22242	0.12358	-0.00089	-0.00011
RC_STD	0.0147	0.0034	-0.0188	-0.000064
Phase RC_STD	-2.26466	0.23131	0.00055	0.00013
E11	0.0208	0.0032	-0.0408	-0.00013
Phase E11	0.22543	0.15134	-0.00034	-0.000052
CF DUT	0.9994	Combined Uncertainty		0.0027
		Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)		0.0054

Frequency: 1 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF STD	0.9844	0.0018	1.0082	0.0018
Pow DUT	0.9169	0.0013	1.0823	0.0014
Pow STD	0.9119	0.0013	-1.0884	-0.0014
PM(R1) DUT	1.08368	0.00026	-0.91579	-0.00024
PM(R1) STD	1.086112	0.000039	0.913742	0.000036
 RC_DUT 	0.0091	0.0031	-0.0121	-0.000038
Phase RC_DUT	-0.65692	0.34365	-0.00024	-0.000081
 RC_STD 	0.0146	0.0034	0.0284	0.00010
Phase RC_STD	0.334737	0.232702	0.000060	0.000014
 E11 	0.0145	0.0032	0.0211	0.000066
Phase E11	-0.47729	0.21772	-0.00018	-0.000038
CF DUT	0.9924	Combined Uncertainty		0.0027
		Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)		0.0054

Frequency: 10 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF STD	0.9465	0.0028	1.0236	0.0029
Pow DUT	0.7945	0.0011	1.2194	0.0014
Pow STD	0.7757	0.0011	-1.2490	-0.0014
PM(R1) DUT	1.09580	0.00012	-0.88417	-0.00011
PM(R1) STD	1.09277	0.00020	0.88662	0.00017
 RC_DUT 	0.0114	0.0061	0.0676	0.00041
Phase RC_DUT	0.51649	0.53632	0.00038	0.00021
 RC_STD 	0.0488	0.0064	0.0277	0.00018
Phase RC_STD	-0.9703	0.1310	-0.0034	-0.00045
 E11 	0.0390	0.0062	0.0545	0.00034
Phase E11	2.1642	0.1590	-0.0031	-0.00049
CF DUT	0.9689	Combined Uncertainty		0.0036
		Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)		0.0072

Frequency: 15 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF STD	0.9301	0.0035	1.0406	0.0036
Pow DUT	0.7750	0.0011	1.2487	0.0014
Pow STD	0.7375	0.0011	-1.3124	-0.0014
PM(R1) DUT	1.093558	0.000036	-0.885017	-0.000032
PM(R1) STD	1.08763	0.00023	0.88984	0.00021
 RC_DUT 	0.0439	0.0062	-0.0728	-0.00045
Phase RC_DUT	-0.2874	0.1410	-0.0055	-0.00078
 RC_STD 	0.0096	0.0064	-0.1199	-0.00076
Phase RC_STD	-2.98499	0.66024	-0.00079	-0.00052
 E11 	0.0751	0.0063	-0.0580	-0.00037
Phase E11	-0.7569	0.0839	-0.0063	-0.00053
CF DUT	0.9678	Combined Uncertainty		0.0044
		Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)		0.0088

Frequency: 18 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF STD	0.9254	0.0047	1.0545	0.0050
Pow DUT	0.6962	0.0010	1.4018	0.0014
Pow STD	0.65041	0.00094	-1.50038	-0.0014
PM(R1) DUT	1.116683	0.000082	-0.873893	-0.000072
PM(R1) STD	1.10814	0.00015	0.88063	0.00013
 RC_DUT 	0.0224	0.0061	0.1638	0.0010
Phase RC_DUT	2.2203	0.2747	-0.0040	-0.0011
 RC_STD 	0.0542	0.0064	-0.1973	-0.0013
Phase RC_STD	2.0072	0.1181	0.0075	0.00089
 E11 	0.1243	0.0065	-0.0565	-0.00037
Phase E11	1.7515	0.0523	0.0035	0.00018
CF DUT	0.9759	Combined Uncertainty		0.0058
		Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)		0.012

9.2. Calibration factor (CF) measurement budget for Keysight U2063XA (MY58000117)

Model function (applicable to all frequencies):

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{P_{R1S}}{P_{R1D}} \cdot \frac{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT})\right)}{\left(1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 \cdot |\Gamma_{e11}| \cdot |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD})\right)} \quad (1)$$

Frequency: 50 MHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF STD	1.0000	0.0026	1.0093	0.0026
Pow DUT	0.915	0.013	1.104	0.015
Pow STD	0.9194	0.0013	-1.0978	-0.0015
PM(R1) DUT	1.06836	0.00014	-0.94473	-0.00013
PM(R1) STD	1.08389	0.00030	0.93119	0.00028
RC_DUT	0.0048	0.0029	0.0395	0.00011
Phase RC_DUT	-2.835836	0.593916	-0.000066	-0.000039
RC_STD	0.02911	0.00050	-0.00385	-0.000019
Phase RC_STD	-1.6913	0.0189	0.0012	0.000023
E11	0.0207	0.0029	0.0037	0.000011
Phase E11	0.0288	0.1377	0.0011	0.00016
CF DUT	1.009	Combined Uncertainty		0.015
		Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)		0.030

Frequency: 1 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF STD	0.9943	0.0035	1.0858	0.0037
Pow DUT	0.984	0.014	1.097	0.016
Pow STD	0.9165	0.0013	-1.1780	-0.0016
PM(R1) DUT	1.07552	0.00025	-1.00383	-0.00025
PM(R1) STD	1.08745	0.00030	0.99282	0.00030
RC_DUT	0.0047	0.0029	-0.0365	-0.00010
Phase RC_DUT	0.804187	0.611077	-0.000010	-0.0000064
RC_STD	0.00676	0.00035	-0.01978	-0.0000069
Phase RC_STD	3.00806	0.05177	-0.00021	-0.000011
E11	0.0169	0.0029	-0.0180	-0.000051
Phase E11	-0.86528	0.16842	-0.00022	-0.000037
CF DUT	1.080	Combined Uncertainty		0.016
		Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)		0.032

Frequency: 10 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF STD	0.9636	0.0044	1.1245	0.0049
Pow DUT	0.865	0.012	1.252	0.016
Pow STD	0.7806	0.0011	-1.3881	-0.0016
PM(R1) DUT	1.08755	0.00028	-0.99634	-0.00028
PM(R1) STD	1.10391	0.00021	0.98158	0.00021
RC_DUT	0.0040	0.0026	-0.0724	-0.00018
Phase RC_DUT	-0.58156	0.63759	0.00023	0.00014
RC_STD	0.02760	0.00080	-0.01457	-0.000012
Phase RC_STD	0.4863	0.0290	-0.0025	-0.000072
E11	0.0423	0.0026	-0.0163	-0.000042
Phase E11	1.2428	0.0602	-0.0023	-0.00014
CF DUT	1.084	Combined Uncertainty		0.016
		Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)		0.033

Frequency: 20 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF STD	0.9420	0.0075	1.0941	0.0082
Pow DUT	0.747	0.011	1.380	0.015
Pow STD	0.6932	0.0010	-1.4868	-0.0015
PM(R1) DUT	1.08051	0.00041	-0.95388	-0.00039
PM(R1) STD	1.09704	0.00012	0.93951	0.00011
RC_DUT	0.0604	0.0026	0.0016	0.0000042
Phase RC_DUT	2.1416	0.0430	-0.0046	-0.00020
RC_STD	0.05875	0.00080	0.00078	0.00000063
Phase RC_STD	2.1734	0.0136	0.0044	0.000060
E11	0.0367	0.0026	0.0039	0.000010
Phase E11	2.55144	0.06953	-0.00013	-0.0000088
CF DUT	1.031	Combined Uncertainty		0.017
		Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)		0.034

Frequency: 26.5 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF STD	0.9240	0.0085	1.0654	0.0091
Pow DUT	0.6642	0.0096	1.4821	0.014
Pow STD	0.62985	0.00091	-1.56288	-0.0014
PM(R1) DUT	1.08728	0.00030	-0.90536	-0.00027
PM(R1) STD	1.101294	0.000061	0.893844	0.000055
 RC_DUT 	0.0453	0.0028	0.1270	0.00036
Phase RC_DUT	1.5024	0.0618	0.0024	0.00015
 RC_STD 	0.0601	0.0013	-0.1375	-0.00018
Phase RC_STD	1.88202	0.02164	-0.00014	-0.0000030
 E11 	0.0701	0.0029	-0.0357	-0.00010
Phase E11	1.2425	0.0406	0.0023	0.000092
CF DUT	0.984	Combined Uncertainty		0.017
		Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)		0.034

Appendix.II.E. Participant Report (TRESICAL)

1. PARTICIPANT INFORMATION

Laboratory Name	Trescal A/S
Related Person Name	Torsten Lippert
Telephone No	+45 8720 6969
E-mail	torsten.lippert@trescal.com
Address	Mads Clausens Vej 12, 8660 Silkeborg, Denmark

2. MEASUREMENT DATE

January 2026

3. ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITION

Temperature: (23 ± 2) °C

Relative Humidity: (40 ± 20) rh%

4. TRAVELLING STANDARDS

Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No	Range	Pin Depth
Keysight	N8481A	MY54350008	10 MHz – 18 GHz	4.729 mm
Keysight	U2063XA	MY58000117	10 MHz – 33 GHz	-0.0004"

5. REFERENCES USED IN MEASUREMENT

Instrument Name	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No	Traceability*
Network Analyzer	Keysight	E5080B	MY59202928	Trescal
Power Meter	Hewlett Packard	E4419A	GB36430157	Trescal
Power Meter	Agilent	N1914A	MY53520001	Trescal
Calibration Kit	Hewlett Packard	85052C	3101A00258	Trescal
Calibration Kit	Wiltron	26N50 Load + O/S	203135	Trescal
Power Sensor	Hewlett Packard	8481A	MY41096355	Trescal
Sensor Module	Hewlett Packard	11792A	2124A01488	Trescal

*) Internal calibration. S-parameter & Calibration Factor is traceable to METAS via reference calibration & verification kits and reference power sensors.

Pin depth, connected ports:

N-type: 5.222 mm

3.5mm: -0.0003"

Since the Agilent N1914A Power Meter is not equipped with an USB port, the measurements of the Keysight U2063XA Power Sensor were carried out using the Keysight BenchVue software.

For this to work the BenchVue software had to be shut down during the measurements, so it was not possible to observe the operation of the BenchVue software during the measurements.

6. MEASUREMENT METHOD

The calibration factor was measured using the VBPC software (version 5, 15.10.2025).

Calibration of RF power sensors using vector network analyzer (VNA):

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \frac{P_{DUT} P_{R1S} (1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 |\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT}))}{P_{STD} P_{R1D} (1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2 |\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD}))} \quad (1)$$

In Equation (1):

CF_{DUT} : Calculated calibration factor values of the DUT Power Sensor (PS).

CF_{STD} : Known calibration factor values of the STD PS.

P_{STD} : Power values read from the power meter connected to the STD PS

P_{R1S} : Power values read from R1 inside the port of the VNA used, measured from the STD PS (taken as the applied power value to the STD PS).

P_{DUT} : Power values read from the power meter connected to the DUT PS.

P_{R1D} : Power values read from R1 inside the port of the VNA used, measured from the DUT PS (taken as the applied power value to the DUT PS).

Γ_{STD} : Reflection coefficients of the STD PS.

Γ_{e11} : Source impedance match error terms of the VNA port used.

Γ_{DUT} : Reflection coefficients of the DUT PS.

Θ_{STD} : Phases of the reflection coefficients of the STD PS.

Θ_{e11} : Phases of the source impedance match error term of the VNA port used.

Θ_{DUT} : Phases of the reflection coefficients of the DUT PS.

7. MEASUREMENT RESULT

Keysight N8481, MY54350008:

Frequency	Reflection Coefficient ($(S_{11} = x + jy)$) of the First Power Sensor			
	Real Component x	Real Component Uncertainty (k=2)	Imaginary Component y	Imaginary Component Uncertainty (k=2)
50 MHz	0.0062	0.0032	-0.0237	0.0097
1 GHz	0.0058	0.0100	-0.0002	0.0086
10 GHz	0.0041	0.0039	0.0160	0.0100
15 GHz	-0.0004	0.0010	-0.0538	0.0100
18 GHz	-0.0241	0.0200	-0.0017	0.0084

Keysight N8481, MY54350008:

Frequency	Calibration Factor of the First Power Sensor (k=2)	Uncertainty of CF of the First Power Sensor (k=2)
50 MHz	0.997	0.009
1 GHz	0.993	0.009
10 GHz	0.975	0.013
15 GHz	0.961	0.018
18 GHz	0.977	0.018

Keysight U2063XA, MY58000117:

Frequency	Reflection Coefficient ($(S_{11} = x + jy)$) of the Second Power Sensor			
	Real Component x	Real Component Uncertainty (k=2)	Imaginary Component y	Imaginary Component Uncertainty (k=2)
50 MHz	-0.0033	0.0107	-0.0013	0.0136
1 GHz	0.0031	0.0111	0.0017	0.0133
10 GHz	0.0154	0.0100	-0.0004	0.0033
20 GHz	-0.0475	0.0125	0.0612	0.0159
26.5 GHz	0.0249	0.0102	0.0459	0.0177

Keysight U2063XA, MY58000117:

Frequency	Calibration Factor of the Second Power Sensor (k=2)	Uncertainty of CF of the Second Power Sensor (k=2)
50 MHz	0.983	0.008
1 GHz	1.055	0.009
10 GHz	1.061	0.020
20 GHz	1.011	0.038
26.5 GHz	0.972	0.050

8. UNCERTAINTY BUDGET

8.1. Calibration Factor measurements uncertainty budget

Keysight N8481, MY54350008:

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \frac{P_{DUT} P_{R1S} (1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2|\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT}))}{P_{STD} P_{R1D} (1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2|\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD}))} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 50 MHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF_{STD}	1.000	0.0040	Gaussian	0.9974	3.990E-03
P_{DUT}	0.90888	1.089E-03	Gaussian	1.0973	1.195E-03
P_{STD}	0.91250	1.094E-03	Gaussian	-1.0945	-1.197E-03
P_{R1D}	1.00022	1.30E-08	Gaussian	-0.9971	-1.30E-08
P_{R1S}	1.00022	3.86E-08	Gaussian	0.9971	3.85E-08
Γ_{DUT}	0.024466	0.0050	Gaussian	9.887E-03	4.944E-05
Θ_{DUT}	-1.31600	0.2044	Gaussian	-3.586E-04	-7.330E-05
Γ_{STD}	0.016954	9.000E-04	Gaussian	-1.669E-02	-1.502E-05
Θ_{STD}	-1.95787	5.308E-02	Gaussian	9.873E-05	5.24E-06
Γ_{e11}	0.0088650	0.0089	Gaussian	-4.641E-03	-4.130E-05
Θ_{e11}	-0.84804	1.0040	Gaussian	-2.599E-04	-2.609E-04
CF_{DUT}	0.9974	Combined Uncertainty			4.3427E-03
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.0087

Keysight N8481, MY54350008:

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \frac{P_{DUT} P_{R1S} (1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2|\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT}))}{P_{STD} P_{R1D} (1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2|\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD}))} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 1 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF_{STD}	0.987	0.0040	Gaussian	1.0062	4.025E-03
P_{DUT}	0.79369	9.618E-04	Gaussian	1.2513	1.204E-03
P_{STD}	0.78868	9.561E-04	Gaussian	-1.2592	-1.204E-03
P_{R1D}	1.00021	1.07E-08	Gaussian	-0.9929	-1.06E-08
P_{R1S}	1.00021	1.00E-08	Gaussian	0.9929	9.93E-09
Γ_{DUT}	0.0058454	0.0050	Gaussian	3.142E-02	1.706E-04
Θ_{DUT}	-0.036042	0.8554	Gaussian	-1.064E-04	-9.101E-05
Γ_{STD}	0.011453	1.051E-03	Gaussian	-2.875E-02	-3.022E-05
Θ_{STD}	0.096193	0.1047	Gaussian	2.541E-04	2.660E-05
Γ_{e11}	0.018285	0.0089	Gaussian	-7.961E-03	-7.085E-05
Θ_{e11}	-2.58041	0.4867	Gaussian	1.477E-04	7.189E-05
CF_{DUT}	0.9931	Combined Uncertainty			4.3760E-03
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.0088

Keysight N8481, MY54350008:

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \frac{P_{DUT} P_{R1S} (1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2|\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT}))}{P_{STD} P_{R1D} (1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2|\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD}))} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 10 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF_{STD}	0.946	0.0055	Gaussian	1.0306	5.668E-03
P_{DUT}	0.57390	7.229E-04	Gaussian	1.6987	1.228E-03
P_{STD}	0.56117	7.144E-04	Gaussian	-1.7373	-1.241E-03
P_{R1D}	1.00021	6.01E-09	Gaussian	-0.9747	-5.86E-09
P_{R1S}	1.00021	5.22E-08	Gaussian	0.9747	5.09E-08
Γ_{DUT}	0.016542	0.0050	Gaussian	0.1781	8.905E-04
Θ_{DUT}	1.32369	0.3023	Gaussian	-1.498E-04	-4.528E-05
Γ_{STD}	0.034485	2.056E-03	Gaussian	0.1313	2.700E-04
Θ_{STD}	-1.12401	5.507E-02	Gaussian	-4.194E-03	-2.310E-04
Γ_{e11}	0.091591	0.0158	Gaussian	8.162E-02	1.290E-03
Θ_{e11}	1.86880	0.1725	Gaussian	-4.344E-03	-7.493E-04
CF_{DUT}	0.9749	Combined Uncertainty			6.1904E-03
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.0124

Keysight N8481, MY54350008:

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \frac{P_{DUT} P_{R1S} (1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2|\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT}))}{P_{STD} P_{R1D} (1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2|\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD}))} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 15 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF_{STD}	0.916	0.0080	Gaussian	1.0495	8.396E-03
P_{DUT}	0.52676	6.745E-04	Gaussian	1.8250	1.231E-03
P_{STD}	0.49823	6.444E-04	Gaussian	-1.9295	-1.243E-03
P_{R1D}	1.00021	8.83E-09	Gaussian	-0.9612	-8.49E-09
P_{R1S}	1.00021	1.54E-08	Gaussian	0.9611	1.48E-08
Γ_{DUT}	0.053796	0.0050	Gaussian	-0.1139	-5.695E-04
Θ_{DUT}	-1.57767	9.294E-02	Gaussian	1.750E-05	1.63E-06
Γ_{STD}	0.040003	3.898E-03	Gaussian	-2.444E-02	-9.527E-05
Θ_{STD}	2.91723	6.937E-02	Gaussian	4.434E-03	3.076E-04
Γ_{e11}	0.059058	0.0158	Gaussian	-0.1203	-1.901E-03
Θ_{e11}	1.58046	0.2675	Gaussian	4.451E-03	1.191E-03
CF_{DUT}	0.9614	Combined Uncertainty			8.8890E-03
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.0178

Keysight N8481, MY54350008:

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \frac{P_{DUT} P_{R1S} (1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2|\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT}))}{P_{STD} P_{R1D} (1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2|\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD}))} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 18 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF_{STD}	0.919	0.0080	Gaussian	1.0630	8.504E-03
P_{DUT}	0.48396	6.302E-04	Gaussian	2.0186	1.272E-03
P_{STD}	0.45680	6.020E-04	Gaussian	-2.1387	-1.287E-03
P_{R1D}	1.00020	1.44E-08	Gaussian	-0.9767	-1.41E-08
P_{R1S}	1.00020	9.09E-09	Gaussian	0.9767	8.88E-09
Γ_{DUT}	0.024190	0.0100	Gaussian	-1.007E-02	-1.007E-04
Θ_{DUT}	-3.07127	0.4134	Gaussian	3.058E-03	1.264E-03
Γ_{STD}	0.028470	3.166E-03	Gaussian	0.1239	3.923E-04
Θ_{STD}	1.50049	0.1929	Gaussian	7.967E-04	1.537E-04
Γ_{e11}	0.064908	0.0158	Gaussian	5.061E-02	7.996E-04
Θ_{e11}	-1.72218	0.2434	Gaussian	3.855E-03	9.383E-04
CF_{DUT}	0.9769	Combined Uncertainty			8.8824E-03
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.0178

Keysight U2063XA, MY58000117:

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \frac{P_{DUT} P_{R1S} (1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2|\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT}))}{P_{STD} P_{R1D} (1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2|\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD}))} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 50 MHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF_{STD}	0.9900	0.0035	Gaussian	0.9933	3.477E-03
P_{DUT}	0.90329	1.092E-03	Gaussian	1.0886	1.189E-03
P_{STD}	0.90943	1.226E-03	Gaussian	-1.0813	-1.326E-03
P_{R1D}	1.00022	9.31E-09	Gaussian	-0.9831	-9.15E-09
P_{R1S}	1.00022	9.63E-09	Gaussian	0.9831	9.47E-09
Γ_{DUT}	0.0035449	0.0050	Gaussian	2.181E-02	1.091E-04
Θ_{DUT}	-2.75428	1.4105	Gaussian	1.708E-05	2.417E-05
Γ_{STD}	0.0020809	9.000E-04	Gaussian	-2.097E-02	-1.887E-05
Θ_{STD}	-2.18546	0.4325	Gaussian	1.599E-05	6.92E-06
Γ_{e11}	0.011357	0.0089	Gaussian	2.965E-03	2.639E-05
Θ_{e11}	-0.60481	0.7837	Gaussian	3.308E-05	2.592E-05
CF_{DUT}	0.9833	Combined Uncertainty			3.9084E-03
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.0079

Keysight U2063XA, MY58000117:

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \frac{P_{DUT} P_{R1S} (1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2|\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT}))}{P_{STD} P_{R1D} (1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2|\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD}))} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 1 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF_{STD}	0.9574	0.0035	Gaussian	1.1021	3.857E-03
P_{DUT}	0.85382	1.029E-03	Gaussian	1.2358	1.272E-03
P_{STD}	0.77474	9.468E-04	Gaussian	-1.3619	-1.289E-03
P_{R1D}	1.00021	9.53E-09	Gaussian	-1.0549	-1.01E-08
P_{R1S}	1.00021	1.40E-08	Gaussian	1.0549	1.48E-08
Γ_{DUT}	0.0035399	0.0050	Gaussian	-4.693E-02	-2.347E-04
Θ_{DUT}	0.49620	1.4125	Gaussian	4.594E-05	6.489E-05
Γ_{STD}	0.0032202	9.408E-04	Gaussian	4.748E-02	4.467E-05
Θ_{STD}	0.44976	0.2825	Gaussian	-3.474E-05	-1.059E-05
Γ_{e11}	0.023071	0.0089	Gaussian	-5.732E-04	-5.10E-06
Θ_{e11}	-0.22638	0.3858	Gaussian	1.121E-05	4.32E-06
CF_{DUT}	1.0551	Combined Uncertainty			4.2682E-03
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.0086

Keysight U2063XA, MY58000117:

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \frac{P_{DUT} P_{R1S} (1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2|\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT}))}{P_{STD} P_{R1D} (1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2|\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD}))} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 10 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF_{STD}	0.8555	0.0075	Gaussian	1.2402	9.302E-03
P_{DUT}	0.64047	7.946E-04	Gaussian	1.6566	1.316E-03
P_{STD}	0.51762	6.737E-04	Gaussian	-2.0497	-1.381E-03
P_{R1D}	1.00021	2.26E-08	Gaussian	-1.0608	-2.40E-08
P_{R1S}	1.00021	1.21E-08	Gaussian	1.0608	1.95E-08
Γ_{DUT}	0.015370	0.0050	Gaussian	4.742E-02	2.371E-04
Θ_{DUT}	-0.023567	0.3253	Gaussian	-2.491E-04	-8.103E-05
Γ_{STD}	0.045994	1.550E-03	Gaussian	3.756E-02	5.822E-05
Θ_{STD}	2.06459	4.254E-02	Gaussian	1.530E-03	6.509E-05
Γ_{e11}	0.023624	0.0158	Gaussian	0.1040	1.643E-03
Θ_{e11}	-2.78854	0.6688	Gaussian	1.281E-03	8.567E-04
CF_{DUT}	1.0610	Combined Uncertainty			9.6783E-03
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.0194

Keysight U2063XA, MY58000117:

Model function :

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \frac{P_{DUT} P_{R1S} (1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2|\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT}))}{P_{STD} P_{R1D} (1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2|\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD}))} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 20 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF_{STD}	0.7686	0.014	Gaussian	1.3148	0.01841
P_{DUT}	0.52117	6.692E-04	Gaussian	1.9390	1.298E-03
P_{STD}	0.39330	5.402E-04	Gaussian	-2.5693	-1.388E-03
P_{R1D}	1.00020	1.62E-08	Gaussian	-1.0103	-1.64E-08
P_{R1S}	1.00020	2.47E-08	Gaussian	1.0103	2.50E-08
Γ_{DUT}	0.077479	0.0100	Gaussian	-0.1239	-1.239E-03
Θ_{DUT}	2.23010	0.1291	Gaussian	5.705E-03	7.365E-04
Γ_{STD}	0.042609	3.514E-03	Gaussian	3.884E-02	1.365E-04
Θ_{STD}	0.40273	5.037E-02	Gaussian	5.888E-03	2.966E-04
Γ_{e11}	0.070966	0.0158	Gaussian	-0.1119	-1.768E-03
Θ_{e11}	-1.69661	0.2226	Gaussian	1.159E-02	2.580E-03
CF_{DUT}	1.0105	Combined Uncertainty			0.01883
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.0377

Keysight U2063XA, MY58000117:

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \frac{P_{DUT} P_{R1S} (1 + |\Gamma_{DUT}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2|\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{DUT}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{DUT}))}{P_{STD} P_{R1D} (1 + |\Gamma_{STD}|^2 |\Gamma_{e11}|^2 - 2|\Gamma_{e11}| |\Gamma_{STD}| \cos(\Theta_{e11} + \Theta_{STD}))} \quad (1)$$

Frequency : 26,5 GHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
CF_{STD}	0.7635	0.019	Gaussian	1.2734	0.02419
P_{DUT}	0.39480	5.405E-04	Gaussian	2.4627	1.331E-03
P_{STD}	0.30967	4.606E-04	Gaussian	-3.1396	-1.446E-03
P_{R1D}	1.00018	1.12E-08	Gaussian	-0.9721	-1.09E-08
P_{R1S}	1.00019	1.33E-08	Gaussian	0.9721	1.29E-08
Γ_{DUT}	0.052215	0.0100	Gaussian	-1.426E-02	-1.426E-04
Θ_{DUT}	1.07296	0.1915	Gaussian	-3.051E-04	-5.84E-05
Γ_{STD}	0.035891	2.327E-03	Gaussian	-1.080E-02	-2.51E-05
Θ_{STD}	-0.88605	7.003E-02	Gaussian	3.943E-04	2.76E-05
Γ_{e11}	0.0079246	0.0281	Gaussian	-0.1429	-4.015E-03
Θ_{e11}	-1.46155	3.5459	Gaussian	8.917E-05	3.162E-04
CF_{DUT}	0.9722	Combined Uncertainty			0.02460
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.0492